

CAMEL CARTING : A SUBSIDIARY SOURCE OF INCOME OF CAMEL KEEPERS IN THE HOT ARID BIKANER DISTRICT OF RAJASTHAN.

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ABSTRACT

Camel power for farming use is more economical than a pair of bullocks and in the sandy terrain the camel energy is not only cost effective but also profitable. A pilot survey was conducted in the Bikaner city and in the nearby village Gadwala (an adapted village under TOT by NRCC). A total of 69 farmers from Bikaner and 45 farmers from Gadwala were interviewed for various aspects of carting and its economics. The study revealed the salient characteristic features of camel used under carting and also focused on the differences of camel carting between city and village and socio economic status of camel farmers in the hot arid region. This study identified three major constraints of camel keepers.

The abbreviation of Camel may be expanded as 'C' - Carrier, 'A' - Arid zone, 'M' - Multipurpose, 'E' - Ecofriendly and, 'L' - Livestock. The camel, "Ship of the Desert" uses various adaptive mechanism for survival in the desert. In the dryland ecosystem camel rearing is regarded as a fairly resource for sustenance. The camel possesses many unique qualities which make it distinctly superior to other domestic livestock in the hot arid desert and semi-arid desert ecosystem. Rapid change in agroecological condition and industrialisation in the recent past has its impact on camel management practices. The total world camel population is estimated to be 19.286 million of which India has third highest camel population of 1.52 million² after Somalia and Sudan. Indian camel population is mainly confined to north-western states viz: Rajasthan, Gujrat, Haryana and Punjab (93.12% of total Indian camel) with highest intensity of camel in eleven arid district of Rajasthan (70.13% total Indian camel population)². The camel is a useful component of desert ecosystem where the flora of usually marginal land can hardly meet the requirement of human food and energy. It is associated with social culture of the societies inhabiting in the dry lands. Marketing of camel is an important trade in the Rajasthan where it is widely used as draft animal. Camel carts continue to play a crucial role in the farm economy as a cheap mode of short distance transportation of different agricultural commodities. Since 85% of the gross cultivated area of the Bikaner district is nonirrigated, camel carts hold a significant potential for financing.¹ Aspects of camel management systems have been studied by NRCC regarding utilisation pattern, traditional management, organisation of pastoral societies and indigenous camel health knowledge.¹ Kohler-Rollefson focused on Raikas breeders of Rajasthan.¹ In fact this comparative study had a two fold objectives Viz: 1- To study the main characteristic features of camel used for carting purpose. 2- To study the difference of camel between city and villages and the socioeconomic

status of camel farmers. Similar type of survey were conducted on camel breeders of Laayourie district in Morocco by Michel et al⁷.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Data Collection:

Various aspects of camel carting have been studied through a pilot survey by camel management unit of National Research center On camel (NRCC). This pilot survey was conducted in city area like Bikaner, Krishi Upasage Mandi (KUM) and in near by village area like Gadwala. The Gadwala is an adapted village under TOT project by NRCC, Bikaner. A total of 69 farmers from KUM (Bikaner) and 45 farmers from Gadwala village were interviewed. A two page proforma was filled out for each camel owner.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Farmers residing in the Bikaner or Greater part of city area, reared their camel under semi-intensive system of management and they used their camel cart to transport different agricultural products (grain bags etc) from mandi to purchaser point and farmers inhabiting at village Gadwala used their camel cart to transport different materials (viz: fuel wood, crop yield, fodder, water etc) in the village or surrounding villages and accordingly they were earning money in their day to day life. The popular fodders (Crop residues) used for feeding the cart camel are Moth chara (*Phaseolus aconitifolius*), Guar Phalgathi (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*). Although some farmers from Gadwala village were providing Mumfali chara (*Arachis hypogea*) and camel from this area were browsing Jhal, Khejri and Pala leaves in the rangeland. As a special feeding farmers offered Mollasses, oil (ground nut/seasum), alams (hydrated aluminium Potassium Sulfate salt), and very few progressive farmers also offered Ghee. The major use of camel were carting, ploughing, water carrying and breeding etc. The main objective of camel rearing in Rajasthan is obviously animal power for pulling a cart or ploughing. The primary activity of camel cart owner is agriculture followed by business. Although few farmers are working as labourers (daily wage basis) where as no report regarding this is available from KUM, Bikaner. The the

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ient characteristic features of camel crating are given in
 ble-1. Most of the camel used under carting belonged to
 to 8 years of age at both places. Different age groups

of camel used for carting purpose were presented in
 Fig-2 A similar trend of observation was also found⁹

Table 1. Salient characteristic features of camel carting.

Sl No	Characteristic Features (KUM)	Bikaner (KUM)	Gadwala Vill.
1.	Percent involvement in carting Farmer himself Hired person	85.65 14.35	78.75 21.25
2.	Activity of camel cart farmer (%): Agriculture Business Labourers	84.16 15.84 NA	95.00 2.50 2.50
3.	Average age of camel: (Years)	7.59 3.21	8.69 2.90
4.	sex of cart camel (%): Male - Female -	85.51 14.49	77.78 22.22
5.	Camel breed used for carting (%): Bikaneri Jaisalmere: Non-Descriptive:	82.61 9.70 7.69	87.50 7.25 5.25
6.	Average working time (hrs/day):	7.59 2.13	8.88 1.64
7.	Average working days/year:	235.57 4.85	247.51 5.39

Fig. 1A

Fig. 1B

Fig. 2 : Different age group of camels used for carting purpose in Bikaner and Gadwala

The cost of male cart camel was found to be higher than female camel in both places. The average cost of male camel was Rs 10030 353.40, Rs. 11500 560.45 where as average cost of female camel was

Rs 8000 460.55, Rs. 9150 250.00 in KUM, (Bikaner) and Gadwala village, Respectively. The income from camel carting was estimated to be higher in city area as compared to village area because camel keepers of city area were getting more opportunity to transport different agricultural products than village area. The per day average income from camel carting was Rs. 299.25 31.72 and Rs. 137.20 26.17 in KUM (Bikaner) and Gadwala village respectively. Most of the farmers were purchasing their camel cart on cash payment basis. It was followed by installment basis and few marginal farmers were also purchasing on loan basis (Fig - 1 A & B).

In KUM the charges were based on the total numbers of bags transported. The average carrying cost of each grain bag was Rs. 4.50 ± 1.12 and average bags carried out in each round was 19.00 ± 4.21 bags. The average distance covered by cart camel was 20.50 ± 5.11 Km./day. But in the Gadwala the Charges were based on each trip/ round. It was suggested that camels used as a

draft animal be encouraged in arid regions.⁵

MAJOR CONSTRAINTS

This study identified three major problems of camel cart farmers. The first major problem was non or less availability of fodder for feeding the cart camel due to shortage of common grazing lands. This problem intensified during lean period (March to July). The second major problem was skin infection of cart camel. This was due to Mange (*Sarcoptes scabiei*) infection, and the third major problem was costly treatment of diseases of cart camel. The integrated animal health camp which is conducted regularly at adapted village, Gadwala and improved nutrition has helped to increase the farmer's income through increase camel draftability.)

CONCLUSION

The greatest advantage of this study is to create awareness among the otherwise ignorant farmers regarding the usefulness of camel in carting in drought prone arid - ecosystem. Though the income from the farm is low and the variability in income is high due to the constraining environment. But there is a sign of hope to explore the income through camel carting that exists for turning the farmer's economy viable.

REFERENCES

1. Amresh Kumar (1999) Potential linked credit plan. National Bank For Agriculture and Rural Development, Bikaner Dist. Bikaner. P - 21
2. F.A.O (1997), Production Year book Rome, Italy.
3. G. Laval, Khanna, N.D.; Faye, B. (1998) A typology of camel farming system in Bikaner and Jaisalmer District of Rajasthan, India.
4. Khanna N.D.; Bissa U.K. (1997) Indian camel pastorals production system and it's indigenious knowledge. *Indian Farming* 47 : 28
5. Khanna N.D., Rai A.K.; (1994). In arid region use of camel as draft animal should be encouraged. *Indian Farming* 44 : 23
6. Kohler - Rollefson (1992). The Raikas Dromedary breeders of Rajasthan: A pastoral system in crisis nomadic people. 30 : 74
7. Michel J.F.; Bengouni m.; Bonnet K.; Zro K. Faye B. (1997). Typologic des system de production camelins dans la province de Laayoune au Maroc *Revue Elev. Med. Vet. Pats trop.*, 50 : 313
8. Saley M (1993) Survey of draught camel for carting in an Indian desert town Bikaner and investigation on draught performance of Bikaneri camel, Bikaner, India NRCC. 66p.
9. Tandon S.N.; Khanna N.D.; Bissa U.K.; (1996) To develop suitable management practices for rearing camels. Annual Report (1995-1996). NRCC. Bikaner. P-36.